

INCREASING THE TEACHERS' PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS AS A PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ISSUE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10401969>

Abstract. *In this article, you can find analysis of theoretical research on the stated issues gives grounds to assert that the fully presented volume of necessary theoretical research sometimes studies individual objective and subjective reasons for the shortcomings of the existing system of improving pedagogical skills.*

Keywords: *pedagogical skill, psychology, competence, self-improvement, components.*

The coming third millennium is characterized by the advent of a new era, which implies the need for the individual to build a new system of relationships with society and the surrounding reality. A teacher who implements the tasks of moral education must, on a personal level, correspond to the ideas about the moral personality that exist in our society. Knowledge of moral principles, rules of ethics and morality is not always sufficient in the system of educational work in matters of moral education. This compliance requires the teacher to have a conscious approach to his own professional activities and a constant desire for self-improvement in professional and personal terms.

A teacher in the modern understanding is a high-level professional with a sufficient amount of scientific knowledge, capable of tackling non-standard situations, implementing creative projects, being ready for self-education, and understanding high civic responsibility for the results of professional activities. Many theorists and practical teachers usually pay sufficient attention to this component of pedagogical activity, without which it is impossible to talk about the level of professionalism that modern realities require of a representative of the teaching profession.

It is also necessary to note the importance of interpersonal relationships between teacher and student. The teacher must treat his students from a partnership perspective, in the context of democratic changes in our society. In the context of changing conditions of reality, due to the development of informatization and modern technologies, it is difficult for a teacher who does not pay due attention to issues of self-improvement to function in the modern educational system.

N.A. Dobrolyubov, V.D. Sipovsky, K.D. Ushinsky identified the main directions of activity of public-school teachers. In the works of such scientists as D.D. Semenov, S.I. Miropolsky, P.F. Kapterev, the above postulates were developed both in theory and in practice. [1.]

In the process of training future teachers, the problem of improving pedagogical skills is one of the fundamental ones, as the classics of pedagogical science constantly talked about in their works. The skill of a teacher can be manifested in both classroom and classroom activities, in the process of organizing extracurricular activities, as well as in the process of personal interaction with students, their parents and colleagues. The choice of teaching as an area of professional activity should not be accidental. Experts dealing with the problems of professional burnout speak about the danger of this trend. Only by realizing the social significance of the chosen profession is a teacher able to achieve positive results in the professional sphere, constantly improving and finding new ways to solve pedagogical problems. As part of the professional training of teachers,

this issue lies in the sphere of responsibility of teachers of higher educational institutions. Continuous improvement of personal professional qualities and skills is an ongoing process of developing pedagogical skills. This activity implies a mutual dialogue between teachers and students, which implies a constant exchange of opinions and fruitful cooperation. The teacher must initially prepare future teachers for the fact that their future profession is a constant process of improvement. One of the important components of the professional activity of a higher school teacher can also be defined as a constant scientific search, which requires the manifestation of such personal qualities as the desire for self-improvement, personal activity, and interest in the results of one's own professional activities. The creative, scientific and professional potential of a teacher has a huge impact on the student's personality. When interacting with students, the authority of the teacher and his personal qualities play an important role.

The next period in psychological and pedagogical science can be designated as a time when there was a process of in-depth development of the problem of a teacher's pedagogical skills. In particular, scientists paid attention in their works to the issues of forming a base of pedagogical skills laid in a higher educational institution, which would be necessary for the further practical activities of yesterday's students. Scientific works examined the issues of motivating teachers to improve their teaching skills, touched upon the problems of reflecting their own teaching experience, and also paid significant attention to the forms and methods used in the process of improving pedagogical skills. Many researchers have addressed the problems of novice teachers, graduates of professional and higher educational institutions, since often a novice teacher has to face many problems in his professional activity, primarily associated with a lack of experience in teaching. Issues related to the certification of teaching staff and the development of creative potential of both each teacher and the teaching staff as a whole were also considered. In particular, it is worth noting the fact that during this period a systematic approach to the process of studying educational processes appeared.

The process of learning for adults can be considered special from a pedagogical point of view, since scientific and methodological materials are mostly aimed at children. While there is a sufficient amount of scientific and pedagogical literature focused on methods and forms of teaching children, it is worth noting the lack of sources in this area for adults. It should be noted that there is a difference in the thinking of a child and an adult, as a result of which we consider it necessary to draw a parallel between the characteristics of children's and adult thinking. That is why it is worth recalling that recently a new direction "androgogy" has been actively developing in science, which deals with issues of education, training and development of adults. Psychologists believe that children's thinking is characterized by conclusions "from particular to particular," it is insensitive to contradictions, strives to embrace everything, and is characterized by a spontaneous search and development of intuitive patterns. Considering the thinking of an adult, it can be noted that it is characterized by opposite properties: an adult strives to avoid contradictions, has the ability to consider objects, processes and phenomena independently of each other, his thinking is characterized by the presence of logical thinking and natural intuition at the same time.

The formation of new positions, a broader view of professional activity and the disclosure of the student's creative potential will be facilitated by mastering the methods of mental activity; development of skills to systematize knowledge, generalize, development of abilities to relate the particular and the general, differentiate basic patterns, ability to explain any phenomena from the point of view of science, etc. The process of implementing the voiced points can be carried out

subject to maximum support from teachers in mastering new information. The ability to perceive unfamiliar, new information also seems to be a significant skill for a teacher in the context of improving his teaching skills.

It should be noted that modern practice of improving the pedagogical skills of specialists in educational institutions is developing in the direction of personal orientation. However, often the system for improving the pedagogical skills of teachers is subject to the standards of pedagogical thinking that has lost its relevance, characterized by unity of content and an orientation towards traditional approaches, which, in the end, consolidates the position of outdated pedagogical thinking of teachers in educational institutions.

Some researchers focus on the delayed, prolonged effect, which sometimes manifests itself in the fact that in the process of work there is an increase in the stereotyping of the teacher's attitudes and ways of thinking. With increasing experience, a reverse process of refusal to learn occurs; something new seems quite difficult to a professional; an experienced teacher finds it difficult to overcome himself in the process of learning new techniques, new forms of work. Thus, in order to develop critical thinking, as well as prepare oneself for new information, a program is proposed aimed at developing reflection on one's own professional activities.

It should be noted that in practice there is a certain dependence of the teacher's creative potential on the extent to which his professional thinking is formed. Every moment of a teacher's professional activity implies reflection, which helps to maintain activity in the profession and develop innovative activities. To look at yourself and your activities from the outside, the ability to really see your shortcomings, to anticipate mistakes in the daily routine of professional activity, the presence of these abilities shape teaching practice and the skill of a teacher. A teacher who has the above characteristics will always be in demand in his professional niche and will be able to develop and build a career.

Having analyzed the research of domestic and foreign psychological and pedagogical science on the issue of interest to us, it is worth mentioning the existence of the following didactic principles:

- the integrity of special training of teachers, which should include scientific-theoretical, psychological-pedagogical, special, methodological and general cultural components;
- unity of theory and practice in teaching;
- taking into account motivation in adult education;
- the focus of the system of improving pedagogical skills on the creative development of teachers.

Speaking about the presence of features of the processes that accompany the improvement of pedagogical skills, in situations where it is necessary to take into account the age factor of the teaching staff of an educational institution, one of the most important principles of their self-improvement is the need to rely on their own life and professional experience. In the case when all of the above principles are observed, it is worth talking about the effectiveness of the functioning system.

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